

STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF TAURINE AND ZINCUM COMBINATION DRUG ON SLEEP DURATION IN MODELS OF ACUTE TOXIC HEPATITIS

Amonova Z.X.

Tashkent Medical Academy. Termez branch
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ABSTRACT

Currently, hepatitis is the second most dangerous infectious disease in the world. Despite the rapid development of modern medicine and the use of new modern methods of treating liver diseases, most patients suffer from chronic hepatitis and liver fibrosis, which leads to a deterioration in the socio-economic situation. Despite improvements in the diagnosis and treatment of hepatitis, mortality rates among the population are growing. The article presents the results of a study of the effect of a new combination of taurine and zinc on the antitoxic function of the liver.

Purpose of the study: will determine the effect of taurine on the antitoxic function of hepatocytes in acute toxic hepatitis

Research progress and methods: toxicological, biochemical, and modern computer programs were used in the research work.

The liver detoxification activity was studied using the thiopental test. Changes in sleep duration under the influence of the chemical agent sodium thiopental indicate an increase or decrease in the activity of liver enzymes, which allows us to draw conclusions about the metabolism of cytochrome P-450 associated with the monooxygenase system of hepatocytes. Experimental rats were administered sodium thiopental at a dose of 60 mg/kg (2% aqueous solution prepared extemporaneously) intraperitoneally for 10 days. We explained the antitoxic effect of the liver by the duration of anesthesia, i.e. we determined the duration of the latent period and the recovery period in rats.

The effect of study drug on sleep duration in patients with acute hepatitis C virus infection was assessed by recording sleep duration during the study.

Figure – 1. Effect of the drug taurine on sleep duration in models with acute toxic hepatitis

The obtained data indicate that with intraperitoneal administration of ethaminal or sodium thiopental (1 g) to rats of the control and experimental groups, the duration of anesthesia increased from 49 ± 4.1 min to 167.2 ± 15.4 min, i.e. by 3.41 times (Figure 1). Taurine, when administered at doses of 30 and 70 mg/kg, reduced the duration of sleep from 167.2 ± 15.4 minutes to 138.3 ± 7.2 and 120.1 ± 6.2 minutes, respectively, compared to the control group. In a comparative study, treatment with Essential reduced the duration of sleep by 112.5 ± 2.4 minutes compared to the control group. According to the obtained results, the activity of MOT enzymes in the liver damaged by CCl₄ increased 3-fold, and as a result of drug treatment, their activity decreased by 17.3% and 28.2% under the influence of Taurine (30 and 70 mg/kg), and by 32.8% under the influence of Essential, respectively.

Obtained by the study shows that the new drug under study at a dose of 70 mg/kg has an inducing effect on liver MOT enzymes similar to the drug Essential. This effect of taurine once again proves its hepatoprotective properties.

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